

Military Service – Recruitment

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Portugal is with many difficulties with recruitment for the Armed Forces since the compulsory period of military service for the young people finished by law.

The Forces are served by a professional effective staff (about 4.00 soldiers and 3.000 officers in the Army) respecting the country compromises with NATO.

However, people are getting old and it is necessary to think in ten years because there isn't any attraction by the actual professional and salary in the Forces.

In the three stages of recruitment – applying – selection and incorporation young people do not seem attracted to serve and when applies, give up after in a big proportional quantity.

This is a problem that responsible staff thinks to solve in three ways – Marketing for the young people giving them opportunities to adventure and new experiences – Inviting young people to try war games and instruction in one day as they were soldiers. And for the ones already convinced to apply, to allow them to be counseled by an expert through other time it serves by contract and getting him/her qualifications for after in the civil life apply easily for work having qualifications.

And another bet is being done. How to incentivize feminine applications. A big social study is going on about how to approach this issue.

This is the American way of acting – creating battle heroes and real 12-Inch Soldier Doll ordered by Ronald Reagan to Marvel to create the famous action figure became a Toy Legend. G.I. Joe was an "action figure".

Our approach to recruitment.

To understand the necessity to defend its own country and State a citizen needs to be educated since a child about values.

These values can be grouped in:

- Citizenship / Citizen
- Human Rights
- Democracy / Democratic
- Diversity

- Civil and Political Rights
- Citizenship Education
- Democratic Cultural Rights
- Economic and Social Rights
- Citizenship Spaces
- Equality

The term “citizen” can generally be understood as “person who coexists in a society”, which, however, does not mean that the idea of citizen associated with the nation-state is no longer relevant or applicable.

But, as the nation-state is no longer the sole pole of authority, the need arose to develop a more holistic view of the concept.

This broader sense of “citizen” and “citizenship” provides a potential new model for analyzing the way we live together.

It is, therefore, a question of moving beyond the boundaries of the “nation-state” to the concept of “community”, which encompasses the local, national, regional and international contexts in which individuals live.

In this sense, the terms "citizen" and "citizenship" include the idea of "status" and "role", involving issues related to rights and duties, but also to equality, diversity and social justice.

It is no longer enough to limit the idea of “citizenship” to voting. The concept should also include the full range of actions taken by the individual that impacts the life of the community (local, national, regional and international) and as such requires a public space in which individuals can act together.

Civil and political rights are essentially associated with freedoms and powers available to individuals and which the State undertakes to respect.

Often regarded as the “first generation” of human rights, these rights include the right to liberty and security, the right to justice, the right to presumption of innocence, the right to marry and the right to participate in public life.

They also include the prohibition of torture and other cruel and inhuman treatment, as well as slavery and forced labor.

These rights are internationally enshrined in the Civil and Political Rights Pact that was adopted by the United Nations Assembly in 1966.

The concept of “cultural rights” is globally linked to “identity” issues, which encompass language and all its implications, belonging to groups, communities, and peoples, as well as to heritage.

This concept is the subject of one of the most controversial human rights debates today. Although the multicultural nature of our societies is generally accepted, the political and legal treatment of this reality - that is, the definition of the rights, the rights of the persons who own them and, above all, the rights of the groups responsible for them.

The methodologies that foster critical analysis include activities such as media analysis, debate, project work, etc.

Active learning can be defined as the process of “learning by doing”. It is an educational process in which

The learner, rather than a passive recipient of knowledge, is an active element in the learning process. Individuals or groups learn best when they actively participate in their learning.

Regarding pedagogical methods, several approaches and methodologies are needed. The methods selected should provide the learner with opportunities to think, act and reflect. By including these three dimensions, active learning seeks to take into account the person as a whole.

Associated active learning methods include brainstorming, role-playing games, debates, discussions and project work.

Cooperative learning means learning from and with others. It is social and interactive learning, in which group processes are of the utmost importance. Cooperative learning activities allow individuals to learn together through work on joint projects. This learning can also encourage learners to tackle problems together, reflect and express themselves better.

Educational research can help to better understand the learning process. It can clarify and inform on basic concepts and ideas which, in turn, can support curriculum design in the Member States. You can stretch the assessment by providing opportunities to examine current practices, find out what works well and what could work best. It can underpin democratic practices by ensuring that learners' opinions and ideas about life are examined and documented.

Reflection is the process that allows an individual or group to actively consider what has happened. Reflection participates in a commitment to the idea of reflective learning and action.

The results of a proper civic education

The results of an appropriate education from childhood relate to the understanding (cognitive outcomes), attitudes (affective outcomes) and behaviors (pragmatic outcomes) that ECD intends to convey to each learner, also pursuing goals at a more social level. broad. The terms included in this section are as follows:

- Social Cohesion
- Cognitive Results
- Sustainable Development
- Pragmatic Results or
- Active Participation
- Positive Peace
- Solidarity
- Responsibility
- Affective Results

Sovereignty

Someone must know about how its Nation is organized and the cultural and civic identity.

If a young person knows the meaning of its country's national flag if knows how to sing its national anthem and knows the Nation's history achieves the notion of national identity and Sovereignty.

The country constitution defines what it is National Defense e.g. Portuguese constitutions says that:

1. The Armed Forces shall be responsible for the military defense of the Republic.
2. The Armed Forces are exclusively made up of Portuguese citizens and their organization is unique throughout the national territory.
3. The Armed Forces shall obey the competent sovereign organs, under the Constitution and the law.
4. The Armed Forces are at the service of the Portuguese people, they are strictly non-partisan and their members cannot take advantage of their weapon, their post or their function for any political intervention.

5. It is incumbent upon the Armed Forces, in accordance with the law, to fulfill the international commitments of the Portuguese State in the military sphere and to participate in humanitarian and peacekeeping missions undertaken by the international organizations of which Portugal is a member.

6. The Armed Forces may be required under the law to collaborate in civil protection missions, tasks related to the satisfaction of basic needs and the improvement of the population's quality of life, and in technical-military cooperation in the field. national cooperation policy.

7. The laws governing the state of siege and the state of emergency shall determine the conditions of employment of the Armed Forces when such situations occur.

This means that it is part of duty any Portuguese citizen to belong to the Armed Forces as a reason and defense of Sovereignty, Security and the National Identity.

If sovereignty is seen as extending only over those to whom the sovereign power is democratically accountable, then this principle provides members of any group over which that sovereign power is claimed a right to democratic participation.

Sovereignty is no longer the recognition of power over a people but the collective right of a people to participate in, and benefit from, an independent political community, participating as an equal in the community of nations. To put it another way, sovereignty becomes a human right.

The Global World

The constitutional value that is most under threat is, of course, sovereignty itself.

Sovereignty is being weakened as the forces of globalization ensure that forces outside the walls of the state fundamentally affect, and sometimes determine, what goes on within them.

Sovereignty and the consequential ban on intervention are also being undermined normatively.

As an essentially Westphalia construct, modern ideas of sovereignty predate the Enlightenment by one hundred years. The greatest threat to sovereignty and the associated stigma attached to intervention lies in the full implementation of Enlightenment values.

There were many reasons for this limited role of Enlightenment values in international law. Initially, democratic nations sought the protection of sovereignty against autocratic states that might intervene to crush their fledgling democracies.

They inclined to keep domestic political values out of international law lest the major views of other states (for example, in favor of monarchies) might be imposed on them.

Recruitment and Mobilization - A Necessary Reflection

Military institutions are their channels through which nations employ national power following the principles that they guide them and thus give their own characteristics
Institutions

Characteristic aspects of the foundation are:

- Armed Forces and its basic composition;
- functional-legal subordination to the supreme authority of the Head of State, through the Ministry of Defense;
- principles of hierarchy and discipline, which guarantee the cohesion of Armed Forces, are the pillars of the Military Institutions;
- constitutional destination, limiting the sphere of action of the Armed Forces and guiding their attributions, as elements of the of the implementation of the National Defense Policy; and
- permanence, imposing its links with the past, especially with their traditions, turning them into the future, but always reflect the national character and its historical vocation.

The Armed Forces find their legal basis in the Constitution and in other legal texts of the Country, which establish their organization, their destination, and its operation. Such documents form a set of which completes and deepens the ground under examination.

The Armed Forces Are the Essential Component of Expression Military of the National Power. They consist of the Navy, the Army and by the Air Force, under the supreme authority of the President of Republic through the Ministry of Defense, are intended to defend the Homeland, the guarantee of constitutional powers and, on the initiative of any of these, law and order, as well as cooperation with the National Development and Civil Defense, and participation in International Operations.

The organization covers the big commands, the commands of forces, organs, establishments, parks and arsenals, units operational and logistical support, considering their staffing and their material endowments.

Articulation means the military device resulting from the location of its units and organs within the National Territory. There are Nations, however, that articulate their Forces, also, in areas of interest and liability outside their Territory.

The articulation of the Armed Forces usually aims to respond to different employment needs, including the occurrence of armed conflict within a national or international context International. It is possible to adapt the articulation to the needs both in the field of development and

Security and which may lead to another form of employment of the Armed Forces: These are the activities known as Complementary Actions, in which the intended direct effects are not typically military.

These complementary actions fall within the constitutional destination of the Armed forces. Such actions are considered to be of national interest and are felt directly in the field of development. The works are mainly in health, education, transportation and They also represent preventive measures to prevent Internal security.

One of the most important features of Military Structure should be flexibility to cope with the most diverse situations internal or external.

Command and Control Capability

The result of adequate general and vocational training to continuous improvement and rigorous selection in the exercise of command, direction or leadership, command and control able to reflect the value of an Armed Force, all your ranks. In this case, the importance of the High Command, for the decisive role in formulating the Policy and Strategy of each Singular Force.

Recruitment and Instruction

Instruction is the process by which they are transmitted technical knowledge about attitudes to be adopted in certain situations and about the use and maintenance of equipment, both individual as well as collective.

After Instruction comes Training, which means exercising the Man, either individually or as a team, developing skills to accomplish specific missions.

Instruction and training must be diversified, objective and well-structured in order to proficiently prepare the military to the missions you may receive. In addition, they enhance your civic training and endow them with qualifications of interest to the Work All levels, whether execution, planning or of command are subject to Instruction and Training. Looking to

Training efficiency and integration, there is a need for frequent combined or joint exercises. Commitment means having the right train to mission and possess the necessary logistic means to Immediate employment. It is, therefore, the degree of readiness, readiness, respond to emergency situations without of mobilization.

Operational capacity and efficiency of logistical support basically depend on Instruction and Training . A good Training can, in terms, overcome a material deficiency. The contrary, however, is not true.

Military Morale

The National Moral, collective state of mind in a given at the moment is more or less unstable according to the influences circumstances that can strengthen or weaken it.

The same is true of Military Morality, a function of conjuncture and reflection of national morality, which is felt in the spirit of sacrifice, firmness of mind and determination to fulfil the mission received.

Discipline, psychological preparation, leadership by commanders and trust in well-run institutions strengthen Moral arousing the spirit of body and conviction of legitimacy of the fight.

Mobilization

The old meaning of the word Mobilization, originated from the Mobilization was restricted to the military - to set in motion or to pass the troops to the "ready to war". The Military Mobilization stood out, for the first time when General von Scharnhorst, after analyzing in detail the reasons for the defeat of the Prussian forces against the Napoleon's troops, created a Mobilization Division in the General Staff of the Prussian Army, a fact that greatly contributed to the victory of that country in the Franco-Prussian War in 1870.

World War II, with its demand for all kinds of means As a consequence, it brought greater responsibilities for Mobilization, whose planning has become more meticulous and the encompass all the national economical, financial and logistical sectors.

Conflict is the starting point for the process evolutionary result of the current conception of National Mobilization.

The National Mobilization, according to this conception, besides the strengthening of the National Power, also aims to meet, within resource requirements in all Expressions for carrying out emergency actions for the direct benefit of National Security.

The emergence of conflicts has not yet been prevented, either under the wars, such as economic, psychological or other aggression, threatening the tranquillity and security of nations.

Involved a community in a situation that endangers its survival, it is imperative to react to neutralize or eliminate the threat.

The action of preventing, neutralizing and eliminating threats that arises in the life of nations should not be at the taste of improvisations, since in this way the National Sovereignty itself would be compromised and the enemy's action stimulated by the opponent's imprudence.

The preparation of actions related to National Defense is, therefore a continuing requirement, varying according to the intensity of the obstacles. Hence the great mutability of these actions and the means of every order necessary for its accomplishment.

The execution, with varying intensities, of the Strategic Actions Defense, requires nations to maintain some means permanently focused on that purpose and at the same time have mechanisms capable of reinforcing them, with the production of new means and with the transfer of others hitherto employed in the Development.

By providing the means for Strategic Actions, common or Logistics relies on the structure of the state and the rules that preside over their relations with natural or legal persons governed by private. However, in the face of an abnormal situation capable of disturbing social harmony, in the face of the imminence or the outbreak of a war, in which the means foreseen and allocated by Logistics are insufficient to overcome the obstacles, the State may activate another mechanism which is the National Mobilization.

In the present age a war can begin without the long periods of political tension and without the foreshadowing incidents of common borders of the past. It has been a very common practice in lately, the commencement of military operations without prior and formal declaration of war.

As a result, the deadlines for execution Mobilization became extremely critical and constitute of great importance, requiring that it be planned and prepared from the Peace time.

In the outbreak of World War II, the idea of to establish obstacle lines and to employ forces retarding to gain the time needed for Mobilization.

The speed of the first operations showed that such a resource alone is not enough. Certain situations may require shorter deadlines and sometimes even before the first war actions precede the beginning of hostilities. Consequently, certain measures should be taken before, regardless of the acts of implementation of the National Mobilization

This gave rise to a new meaning for National Mobilization, which came to be conceived as a necessary, permanent activity, methodical and progressive, essential to national security and capable of influencing development when necessary.

National Mobilization is conceptualized as follows:

Set of planned activities oriented and undertaken by the State, from the normal situation, complementing the National Logistics, with the purpose of enabling the Country to carry out strategic actions in the field of National Defense, to deal with foreign aggression.

Conclusion

1 – Recruitment, either voluntary or compulsory is the base of the military institution as we tried to explain.

2 – A Recruit that does not understand why he is being instructed and trained will never engage a fight for its country's sovereignty because he was not properly educated since the child not knowing the cultural values of the Nation, the State, and the Constitution.

3 - Education from childhood is the base of National Defense and of the Military Institution, even when the soldiers have temporary contracts.

4 – A recruit learns about the military institution, about its function and about the dangers that can threaten its country and even is willing to fight to death not to submit its country to the enemy.

5 – If education does not identify the National values of national Identity, National Culture, and National History any Government if necessary a general mobilization will not succeed.

6 – These very important issues must be topics of discussion of the civil society from where will be recruited the soldiers and to, after finishing the contract they will be integrated.

7 – Is not a Reagan way inventing plastic heroes for young generations, that will accomplish the defense and security of a nation.

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